

PERCEPTIONS OF TEACHERS ON THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION

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Abstract. The study aimed to understand teachers' perceptions of using digital technology in their classrooms. The study focuses on three main themes: attitudes and beliefs, professional development, and effective professional development programs. Additionally, the study explores how teachers cope with the challenges of using digital technology in their instruction through Pedagogical Approaches, Challenges and Barriers, and Student Outcomes, the study drawn educational insights from its findings regarding digital pedagogy and instructional practices, contextual factors, and differentiated instruction. The research disclosed the findings based on the data gathered from of ten (10) participant's line-up of public elementary school faculty. Addressing these areas can contribute significantly to the successful integration of digital technology in classroom instruction, ultimately enhancing the quality of education provided to students. The study's findings have important implications for various aspects of education, including teacher training programs, professional development initiatives, pedagogical innovation, addressing challenges and barriers faced by teachers when integrating technology into their teaching methods, improving student outcomes through effective use of digital tools, influencing educational policies related to technology integration in schools at different. Ultimately, this research can contribute significantly towards enhancing education quality provided by successfully integrating digital technologies into classroom instructions which prepares students in an increasingly technological world.

KEY WORDS

1. Perceptions of teachers 2. digital technology 3. classroom instruction

1. Introduction

Digital technology has become integral to modern education, transforming teaching and learning in elementary classrooms. In recent years, the widespread availability of digital tools and resources has significantly impacted educational practices, offering new avenues for instruction, engagement, and student-centered learning. The use of digital technology in elementary education has the potential to enhance students' educational experiences and prepare them for a technology-driven world. In a global context, elementary school teachers' competency establishment trends include digital, creative thinking, and communication skills. Digital literacy skills are required to get special attention in developing four pedagogical teachers' competencies so that teachers can keep pace with the development of time and the tendency of students' characteristics. In this case, education stakeholders should show stability to schools to help develop the competencies teachers must have in the 21st century. Contributions

that could be made to realize the expectations of classroom teachers are underlining the importance of integrating digital technology into elementary school learning. Therefore, perfect collaboration between all educators, stakeholders, parents, and the parties in the education environment is needed. The main focus is innovations to improve teachers' competencies in Indonesia in technological and information development (Del-Moral-Pérez et al., 2019). Current learning patterns illustrate that not all teachers apply digital-based learning in the classroom. Some study results mention that the integration of digital technology in education has obstacles, in which teachers are not able to utilize digital technology in the school due to a lack of knowledge, skills, training, self-confidence, and limited facilities (Amuko Miheso-O'Connor, 2015; Hadriana, 2017; Mirzajani, Mahmud, Ayub, Luan, 2015) The 21st century demands innovation in the learning process (Wahyudi, 2019). The global community has yet to explore many things related to digital technology's position in the eyes of educators and education stakeholders. Some elementary school-level studies in Indonesia note that learning has been equipped with digital-based facilities, including computers and the Internet. Still, not all levels integrate digital-based learning because some teachers only use it as an administrative function (Mundy, Kupczynski Kee, 2012). In the United States, as Reported by Go Guardian (2023), technology is a constantly evolving industry, and education technology can quickly become obsolete as new technology is introduced. A major barrier many teachers struggle with when introducing technology into their classrooms is keeping up with these many changes and trends. The team at GoGuardian was dedicated to staying on top of these trends and improving products with the most up-to-date solutions for schools, as they understand the importance of integrating technology in the classroom. They added that technology is being utilized more frequently in K-12 education, many teachers are still struggling to integrate it into their classrooms and questioning whether doing so is the right move for them. A number of factors that must be considered would impact decisions about how, when, and if we should introduce new technology (Go Guardian, 2023), Supported by San Jose's ideas (2020), this study explores how teachers perceive the use of digital technology in their classrooms, examining their attitudes towards technology integration, perceived benefits and drawbacks, levels of confidence, and professional development needs. By capturing the voices and experiences of teachers, this research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities surrounding the use of digital technology in elementary education and inform educational policymakers, administrators, and other stakeholders. Moreover, in conclusion, understanding teachers' perceptions on the use of digital technology in elementary classrooms is crucial for guiding educational policies, curricular decisions, and professional development initiatives. By exploring teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and experiences, this research sheds light on the potential of digital technology to improve teaching practices, engage students, and foster meaningful learning experiences in the elementary education landscape (Dela Cruz, Barrot, 2019). In the national context, the integration of digital technology in classroom instruction has become increasingly important in the Philippines due to the implementation of the K-12 Basic Education Program. Several studies have investigated the perceptions of junior high school teachers on the use of digital technology in instruction in the Philippines (Balansag Basco, 2020). These studies have explored various factors that influence the use of digital technology in the classroom, such as teacher readiness, infrastructure, and pedagogical practices. Many studies have found that teacher readiness is crucial in effectively integrating digital technology in instruction. This includes factors such as

teachers' beliefs and attitudes toward digital technology, their technical skills, and their confidence in using technology in the classroom (Nisnisan Tampus, 2021). In the local context, in a study conducted by Gumapac and Olfindo (2019) entitled "Perceived Benefits and Challenges in Integrating Digital Technology: Basis for a Proposed Program for Professional Development of Teachers," they found that teachers in Davao City generally had positive perceptions towards the use of digital technology in instruction. They perceived digital technology as useful for enhancing students' engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. However, the study also revealed that some teachers lacked the necessary skills and knowledge to integrate digital technology into their instructional practices effectively. In addition, infrastructure issues such as inadequate internet connectivity and limited access to devices also hindered the effective integration of digital technology in the classroom. Another study by Calanog and Matubis (2020), "The Use of Digital Technology in Davao City," also reported similar findings. They found that most teachers in Davao City recognized the potential benefits of using digital technology in instruction, such as improving students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, they also identified several challenges to effective technology integration. These include inadequate training and support, lack of access to devices and internet connectivity, and the need for more relevant and engaging digital content.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study, "Perceptions of Teachers on the Use of Digital Technology in Elementary Classrooms," examined teachers' current perceptions, experiences, and challenges regarding integrating digital technology in elementary education. Considering the rapid advancements and changes in educational technology, the study aims to provide up-to-date insights into teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and practices related to using digital tools and resources in the classroom.

- (1) What are teachers' lived experiences on using digital technology in classroom instruction?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction?
- (3) What educational management insight and practices can be drawn from the study?

1.2. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored with the theory of Mishra Koehler (2006). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) This theory emphasizes the importance of teachers' knowledge and understanding of the intersection between technology, pedagogy, and content to effectively integrate technology in teaching and learning, including the characteristics of the innovation, the characteristics of the adopters, and the communication channels used to disseminate information about the innovation. Secondly, this study was anchored with the theory of Rogers, (2003). Diffusion of Innovations Theory. This theory focuses on adopting and spreading new ideas or innovations over time. The theory posits that the adoption of innovation is influenced by several factors. Secondly, this study was anchored in Bandura's (1997) Self-Efficacy Theory. This theory suggests that individuals' beliefs in their own abilities to perform a particular task influence their behavior and outcomes. In the context of technology integration in education, teachers' self-efficacy beliefs can influence their willingness to adopt and use new technologies in their teaching practices. Lastly, this study was also anchored in Bandura's (1986) Social Cognitive Theory. This theory emphasizes the role of social interactions and observations in shaping individuals' attitudes, beliefs, and be-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

haviors. In the context of technology integration in education, teachers’ perceptions of their peers and school leaders’ norms and expectations could influence their willingness to adopt and use new technologies in their teaching practices. Shown in Figure 1 is the interconnection between the two research questions, Teachers’

lived experiences on using digital technology in classroom instruction and challenges in exploring digital technology in classroom instruction that would result in the common denominator which is Insights Learned from their experiences.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the researcher introduced philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, data collection and analysis, ethical considerations, the role of the researcher, and trustworthiness. In line with contemporary ethical standards in research, the researcher employed artificial intelligence (AI) tools to assist in the proofreading process of this paper. The use of AI for proofreading was conducted to ensure accuracy, enhance clarity, and maintain a high standard of academic writing. This step was taken to minimize human errors, which aligns with the evolving ethical guidelines that advocate for the use of advanced technologies in research to improve the quality and integrity of academic work. By disclosing the use of AI in the proofreading process, the researcher adheres to principles of transparency and integrity, thereby contributing to the ongoing discourse on ethical research practices in the digital age.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—I

It was assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. It was further assumed that the sample used for this study was representative of in-depth and focus group interviews in a face-to-face manner as a medium of communication. These assumptions have been articulated throughout the last 20 years in various qualita-

tive research (Denzin Lincoln, 2011) and as the “axiomatic” issues advanced by Guba and Lincoln (1988) as the guiding philosophy behind qualitative research. These beliefs have been called paradigms, philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, ontologies, broadly conceived research methodologies, and alternative knowledge claims (Creswell, 2014). There were be-

liefs about ontology, the nature of reality, epistemology, what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified, axiology (the role of values in research), and methodology (the process of research). In this discussion, I first discuss each of these philosophical assumptions, detail how they might be used and written into qualitative research, and then link them to different interpretive frameworks that operate at a more specific level in the research process. Evidence of multiple realities includes using multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. **Ontology.** The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. When researchers conduct qualitative research, they embrace the idea of teachers' perceptions of using digital technology in classroom instruction. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study intending to report these multiple realities. For example, writers compile a phenomenology report on how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994). **Epistemology.** Conducting a qualitative study means that the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the study participants. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I chose these elementary teachers as my participants is because I

have known them for quite a long time. This is how knowledge was known through the subjective experiences of people. It becomes important to conduct studies in the "field" where the participants live and work; these were important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the "field" or get to know the participants, the more they "know what they know" from firsthand information. For example, good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2008). In short, the researcher tries to minimize the "distance" or "objective separateness" (Guba Lincoln, 1994) between himself or herself and those being researched. **Axiology.** This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the study's value-laden nature and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the results of this study were shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they "position themselves" in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, I was apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989). I believe that I am more qualified to conduct this study since I have ample experience teaching in junior high school.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The researcher made these qualitative assumptions, which were the methods used in the process of qualitative research (Creswell 2003). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and based on the researcher's own experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the researcher's values. Raw textual data is condensed into a brief summary for-

mat through an inductive approach. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes the meaning of the lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2003) was used in this study. A phe-

nomenological study intends to understand and describe an event from the participant's point of view. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how group or community members interpret themselves, the world, and the life around them (Mertens, 2005). The purpose of this study is to explore teachers' perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. These results may provide foundational information to guide the district in addressing the

local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it enables them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for teachers in exploring teachers' perceptions of digital technology in classroom instruction. In addition, this study's perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction appear to have experience in the areas of building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

2.3. Design and Procedure—In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures will be described so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the study's time, place, context, and culture were thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which is the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2005). This section discusses the interview approach, explains the role of the researcher, and, lastly, describes the sampling method and ethical considerations. Semi-Structured Interviews. Patton (2015) proposes that researchers conduct interviews to learn what they cannot directly observe. Qualitative interviewing is not used to get answers to questions but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience. Generally, qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the use of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific, more focused information (Schwandt, 2001). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with

directionality and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul LeCompte, 1999). This study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore teachers' perceptions of using digital technology in classroom instruction. An interview guide was used to ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview, but when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing several participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining the issues to be explored (Patton, 2015). The open-ended questions were framed in a way, so the participants could represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms, in addition to taking the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2015). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for transcription purposes. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—

This study comprises ten (10) participants from the public elementary school faculty lineup who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The participants would join for an in-depth interview (IDI). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools were purposefully selected. The researcher used purposive sampling, also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling, a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. This

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical standards were required in conducting research; thus, this phenomenological research adheres to the Belmont Report (1979) principles, which strictly observe the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this study was subjected to the evaluation of the the college where the researcher is studying, Inc. – Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) for the full board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation as regards the dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vilification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities and community involvement. Social Value. The researcher investigated and carefully analyzed one of the pressing problems in our educational system. This research also concerns teachers’ perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. This study is expected to provide important information in recognizing the extent and type of experiences that elementary teachers have had. The findings of this study could provide the best role of exploring teachers’ perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. The researcher was hopeful that the output of the study would be relevant not only to the participants but also to the school. The study result would be presented in the local, national, and even international fora and, if given a

survey sampling method requires researchers to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies to properly choose and approach eligible participants to be conducted (Denzin, 2017). This study’s participants were elementary school teachers from the selected public schools in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Below is a simple description of the participants: Participants were licensed professional teachers who live in Panabo City and have experience teaching for three or more years.

chance, be published in an international publication. Informed consent. In this study, informed consent was secured from all the participants who were involved. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to twelve (12) elementary school teachers. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The participants had sufficient information and an adequate understanding of both the proposal and the implications of their participation in the study. Codes were assigned to individuals in the data presented. Every page of the transcriptions of the in-depth interview and focus group discussions was signed by the researcher to attest that the key informant interviews were done with the consent of informants. In addition, the informants were accorded the needed respect. The researcher made it a point that the form must bear the signature of the participant or agreement, which would imply that she participated in the study voluntarily. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and/or forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect. Thus, they were informed ahead that they may withdraw their participation in the study and if ever inconvenience were felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they

would be given the chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher was at an elementary school in Panabo District, Division Panabo City, one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so that they were not vulnerable while participating in this study. The researcher considered elementary school teachers to be participants in this study because they were mature enough to decide for themselves whether to partake in this study or not.

Risks-Benefit Safety. A careful assessment of foreseeable risks, burdens, and benefits to the participants was made. The questionnaire that the researcher administered did not contain any degrading, discriminating, or unacceptable language that was offensive to the participants so that the risks were avoided. An extra careful approach was used in collecting the data so that irrelevant and confidential details were rejected. The study did not involve any high-risk situation that the participants may experience in their social and emotional needs. Further, this study ensured that the potential benefits of the participants were greater than the potential harm. The results of this study would benefit the entire Department of Education, including teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the teachers' perceptions and experiences in exploring their perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. Practically, the researcher identified only minimal risks, if not negligible, regarding physical harm or discomfort they may experience during the study. Specifically, whatever might cause adverse effects on personal relationships, loss of status, privacy, or time of the respondents were taken into consideration in the planning stage of the conduct of the study so that such things would be minimized if not prevented

fully. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The current study ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the information of the respondents. The researcher adhered to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or Republic Act 10173, which mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in collecting, retaining, and processing personal information (Congress of the Philippines, 2012). This act protected the fundamentals of human rights regarding information privacy, ensuring the free flow of information that promotes innovation and growth. The researcher protected the respondent/participants' right to privacy, wherein their responses were given with the highest respect. Unless the law requires, the confidentiality of information shall always be observed. Other personal information will not be asked in the study to safeguard their identities and enable them to participate without fearing the revelation of involvement in the study. Any information was taken with utmost care to ensure the data sources' anonymity and de-identify any personal information that would be shared. Such names and identities were protected by using a pseudonym. Tracing these codes' information was reflected in an archival log. Hence, personal names were not used to trace the identification. Written responses, if any, were captured through a camera. Recordings were saved, and documents were kept in one place, protected or encrypted.

Justice. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in the choice of population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of their economic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. The researcher provided just compensation and reimbursement for data used and costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed of the

study's objectives before they were involved in the process. It was emphasized that they were the data source and encouraged to give honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority for the benefits of the possible offshoots of the study findings. Transparency. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by ensuring that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially the information that has a bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent. The participants can access and scrutinize the study's findings if the findings are scientifically valid and have significant implications for the participant's well-being. The researcher assured us that the study was conveyed in full scope and accurately. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to the Department of Education, teachers, students, parents, and the community. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher is ultimately responsible and accountable for the research. For the research to be carried out with the necessary skills and knowledge. I am aware of the limits of personal competence in research. I have experience as an elementary school teacher in one of the public schools in Panabo District, Division of Panabo City. I attended several research-related seminars and training, which I consider an asset in conducting this study with the assistance of my adviser and colleagues, readings from various books and literature, fulfilling my duties and responsibilities at RMC as an elementary school teacher and the supervision of RMC-REC, I acquired the knowledge and skills needed to conduct the research. Also, the supervision and direction of

his adviser and the panelists helped improve the research study. The researcher's adviser is an expert in this study. Therefore, the adviser is a big help to complete the study with the quality of the content. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher is adequately equipped with the budget and equipment needed to conduct the study. This ensures that the researcher has the best facilities to complete the research. The laptop, printer, internet connection, and other necessary facilities are personally owned by the researcher, making them adequately and readily available. Furthermore, non-online and online library resources are readily available, such as books and Google. In addition, if possible, Google Meet was used to gather the data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some experts provided the researcher with the guidance needed to conduct this research, such as the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members, who are also the expert validators. Community Involvement. The researcher is engaged with communities like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public elementary schools is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The RMC graduate school helped correct, validate, and revise the manuscript for the current study. The RMC graduate school provided directions to the researcher based on its research standards and practices. The elementary school teachers participated in developing the questionnaire through the output of the first phase of the study. The guide questions served as the instrument for gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants were observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the output of the study

because they are the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about exploring the perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction.

2.6. Data Collection—Ethical standards were required in conducting research; thus, this phenomenological research adheres to the Belmont Report (1979) principles, which strictly observe the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this study was subjected to the evaluation of the college where the researcher is studying, Inc. – Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) for the full board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation as regards the dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vilification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities and community involvement. Social Value. The researcher investigated and carefully analyzed one of the pressing problems in our educational system. This research also concerns teachers’ perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. This study is expected to provide important information in recognizing the extent and type of experiences that elementary teachers have had. The findings of this study could provide the best role of exploring teachers’ perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. The researcher was hopeful that the output of the study would be relevant not only to the participants but also to the school. The study result would be presented in the local, national, and even international fora and, if given a chance, be published in an international publication. Informed consent. In this study, informed consent was secured from all the participants who were involved. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to twelve (12) elementary school teachers. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The participants had sufficient information and an adequate understanding of both the proposal and the implications of their participation in the study. Codes were assigned to individuals in the data presented. Every page of the transcriptions of the in-depth interview and focus group discussions was signed by the researcher to attest that the key informant interviews were done with the consent of informants. In addition, the informants were accorded the needed respect. The researcher made it a point that the form must bear the signature of the participant or agreement, which would imply that she participated in the study voluntarily. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and/or forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect. Thus, they were informed ahead that they may withdraw their participation in the study and if ever inconvenience were felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they would be given the chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher was at an elementary school in Panabo District, Division Panabo City, one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so that they were not vulnerable while participating in this study. The researcher considered elementary school teachers to be participants in this study because they were mature enough to decide for themselves whether to partake in this study or not. Risks-Benefit Safety. A careful assessment of foreseeable risks, burdens, and benefits to the participants was made. The questionnaire that the researcher administered did not contain any degrading, discriminating, or unacceptable language that was offensive to the participants so that the risks were avoided. An

extra careful approach was used in collecting the data so that irrelevant and confidential details were rejected. The study did not involve any high-risk situation that the participants may experience in their social and emotional needs. Further, this study ensured that the potential benefits of the participants were greater than the potential harm. The results of this study would benefit the entire Department of Education, including teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the teachers' perceptions and experiences in exploring their perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. Practically, the researcher identified only minimal risks, if not negligible, regarding physical harm or discomfort they may experience during the study. Specifically, whatever might cause adverse effects on personal relationships, loss of status, privacy, or time of the respondents were taken into consideration in the planning stage of the conduct of the study so that such things would be minimized if not prevented fully. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The current study ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the information of the respondents. The researcher adhered to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or Republic Act 10173, which mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in collecting, retaining, and processing personal information (Congress of the Philippines, 2012). This act protected the fundamentals of human rights regarding information privacy, ensuring the free flow of information that promotes innovation and growth. The researcher protected the respondent/participants' right to privacy, wherein their responses were given with the highest respect. Unless the law requires, the confidentiality of information shall always be observed. Other personal information will not be asked in the study to safeguard their identities and enable them to participate without fearing the revelation of involvement in the study. Any information was taken with utmost care to ensure the data sources' anonymity and de-identify any personal information that would be shared. Such names and identities were protected by using a pseudonym. Tracing these codes' information was reflected in an archival log. Hence, personal names were not used to trace the identification. Written responses, if any, were captured through a camera. Recordings were saved, and documents were kept in one place, protected or encrypted. Justice. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in the choice of population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of their economic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. The researcher provided just compensation and reimbursement for data used and costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed of the study's objectives before they were involved in the process. It was emphasized that they were the data source and encouraged to give honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority for the benefits of the possible offshoots of the study findings. Transparency. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by ensuring that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially the information that has a bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent. The participants can access and scrutinize the study's findings if the findings are scientifically valid and have significant implications for the participant's well-being. The researcher assured us that the study was conveyed in full scope and accurately. Specifically, in qualitative data

analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to the Department of Education, teachers, students, parents, and the community. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher is ultimately responsible and accountable for the research. For the research to be carried out with the necessary skills and knowledge. I am aware of the limits of personal competence in research. I have experience as an elementary school teacher in one of the public schools in Panabo District, Division of Panabo City. I attended several research-related seminars and training, which I consider an asset in conducting this study with the assistance of my adviser and colleagues, readings from various books and literature, fulfilling my duties and responsibilities at RMC as an elementary school teacher and the supervision of RMC-REC, I acquired the knowledge and skills needed to conduct the research. Also, the supervision and direction of his adviser and the panelists helped improve the research study. The researcher's adviser is an expert in this study. Therefore, the adviser is a big help to complete the study with the quality of the content. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher is adequately equipped with the budget and equipment needed to conduct the study. This ensures that the researcher has the best facilities to complete the research. The laptop, printer, internet connection, and other necessary facilities are personally owned by the researcher, making them adequately and readily available.

2.7. *Data Analysis*—Qualitative data analysis begins with the process of organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2001). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2006) remind

Furthermore, non-online and online library resources are readily available, such as books and Google. In addition, if possible, Google Meet was used to gather the data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some experts provided the researcher with the guidance needed to conduct this research, such as the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members, who are also the expert validators. Community Involvement. The researcher is engaged with communities like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public elementary schools is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The RMC graduate school helped correct, validate, and revise the manuscript for the current study. The RMC graduate school provided directions to the researcher based on its research standards and practices. The elementary school teachers participated in developing the questionnaire through the output of the first phase of the study. The guide questions served as the instrument for gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants were observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the output of the study because they are the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about exploring the perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction.

researchers that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qualitative research. In this last section, the data analysis procedures were explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this

study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic were thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used Marshall and Rossman's (2006) seven phases of data analysis to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the participants' words. The seven phases included organizing the data, immersion in the data, generating categories and themes, coding the data, offering interpretations through analytic memos, and searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2006). Data analysis begins with organizing the data. This process involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in sequence with the order of the interviews, allowing it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to organize the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data through extensive reading of the interviews to understand the content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems comprising categories that divide

some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies were generated from theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs through which to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, I began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences by pulling salient themes, reoccurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believe this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began interpreting the data to find significance and meaning in exploring elementary school teachers' perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. Rossman and Marshall (2006) remind researchers that alternate explanations always exist within the data. Before moving forward, the researcher stops and evaluates the findings for other plausible explanations.

2.8. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Words on the other. The chart should include references to exciting or illustrative quotations. Trustworthiness or rigor of a study refers to the degree of confidence in data, interpretation, and methods used to ensure the quality of a study (Pilot Beck, 2014). Trustworthiness consists of

the components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Researchers should establish the protocols and procedures necessary for a study to be considered worthy of consideration by readers (Amankwaa, 2016). Credibility or confidence in the truth of the study and, therefore, the find-

ings were the most crucial criterion (Polit Beck, 2014). The researcher must link the research study's findings with reality to demonstrate the truth of the research study's findings. The extent to which findings were helpful to persons in other settings and that readers could determine how applicable the findings were to their situations (Polit Beck, 2014). Researchers support the study's transferability with a rich, detailed description of the context, location, and people studied and by being transparent about analysis and trustworthiness. Researchers must provide a vivid picture that informs and resonates with readers (Amankwaa, 2016). Dependability refers to the data's stability over time and the study's conditions (Polit Beck, 2014). It was

the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. Conformability was neutrality or the degree to which findings are consistent and could be repeated. It was analogous to the objectivity of research during data collection and analysis. There must be congruency between two or more independent persons about the data's accuracy, relevance, or meaning (Polit Beck, 2012). Conformability also indicates a means to demonstrate quality.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—Framework analysis was a specific qualitative technique initially developed by Liz Spencer, Jane Ritchie, Jane Lewis, and Lucy Dillon for the National Centre for Social Research to help the UK government with an evidence-based policy-making method. These techniques are used for government social research to ensure quality standards in qualitative evaluation methods. Due to its format, framework analysis is particularly suitable for applied policy and health research. Framework Analysis is more prescriptive than other research methodologies as it provides a more step-by-step approach and is primarily used for applied research. The feature that differentiates framework analysis from other qualitative analysis techniques is its use of a matrix output that enables researchers to analyze data by participants and themes systematically. In the matrix, rows represent individual participants, and columns represent themes. The cell of the matrix was used by the researcher to summarize their findings about the corresponding participant and theme. This matrix enables researchers to contextually compare and contrast data across participants and themes (Hackett,

Alison Strickland, Karen, 2018). The framework has been designed to be applied to appraisals of the outputs of qualitative evaluation reports, papers, and journal articles, although it would also have some relevance to assessments of proposals or study conduct. Although the four guiding principles would be relevant to any qualitative research method and, in many cases, to quantitative research too. the appraisal questions and quality indicators are designed to focus on four methods: in-depth interviews, focus groups, observation, and documentary analysis. Familiarization was becoming familiar with the data through reading and re-reading interview transcripts. Familiarizing the whole interview with the audio recording and transcript and any contextual or reflective notes the researcher recorded was a vital stage in interpretation. It could also be helpful to re-listen to all or parts of the audio recording. The researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, exploring the field, or reading transcripts. The researcher would become aware of critical ideas and recurring themes throughout the procedure and would make a note of them. The researcher may be unable to review all of the material due

to the enormous amount of data that might be collected in qualitative research. As a result, a portion of the data set would be utilized. Several elements of the data collection method would influence the selection. Coding was the process of summarizing and representing data in order to provide a systematic account of the recorded or observed phenomenon. After familiarization, the researcher carefully reads the transcript line by line, applying a paraphrase or label that is a 'code' that describes what they have interpreted in the passage as necessary. Coding aimed to classify all of the data to be compared systematically with other parts of the data set. Developing a thematic framework happens after coding a few transcripts. The researcher needs to compare the labels applied and select a set of codes to apply to all subsequent transcripts. Codes could be grouped into categories, which are then clearly defined. This forms a working analytical framework. Several iterations of the analytical framework were likely required

before no additional codes emerged. It was always worth having another code under each category to avoid ignoring data that does not fit; the analytical framework was never 'final' until the last transcript had been coded. Indexing involves identifying portions or sections of data that relate to a specific theme. This procedure is conducted using all textual data collected, such as transcripts of interviews. Ritchie and Spencer, as cited by Goldsmith, (2021) suggest using a numerical system to index references and annotating them in the margin beside the text for ease. Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for this task. Charting involves summarizing the data by category from each transcript. Good charting requires an ability to strike a balance between reducing the data on the one hand and retaining the original meanings and 'feel' of the interviewees' words on the other. The chart should include references to interesting or illustrative quotations.

The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, includes an analysis of the important qualities depicted in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, assisting the researcher in interpreting the data set. I must be cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis and define concepts, map the range and nature of phenomena, create typologies, find associations, provide explanations, and develop strategies

(Ritchie Spencer, as cited by Goldsmith, 2021). These concepts, technologies, and associations mirror the participant. Therefore, any strategies or recommendations the researcher offers reflect the participants' real views, beliefs, and values. Figure 2 shows the steps in the process of developing the study's analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, which focused on the perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction was gathered to specifically; this study sought to answer the following questions: What are teachers' lived experiences on using digital technology in classroom instruction? How do teachers cope with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction? What educational management insight and practices can be drawn from the study? Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used as I presented the quotations based on the study participants' responses. In reference to the transcriptions of the interviews, I

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

used codes to refer to participants in the research question. Their responses were contained and bounded around the study's three (3) research questions. Moreover, participants' responses were transcribed verbatim, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to a schema. The first objective of this study was to learn about the teachers' lived experiences and perceptions of teachers' use of digital technology in classroom instruction. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, which have three major themes: attitudes and beliefs, professional development, and effective professional development programs.

3.0.1. Welcoming Attitudes and Beliefs— It should start when seeking to integrate technology effectively in K to 12 school systems. Often, we gravitate towards tools, hardware, and processes. While those are necessary and important, I think we need to lay a more secure foundation when thinking about teachers and their classroom technology integration. Effective technology integration begins with one's attitudes and beliefs. Just as our attitudes and beliefs impact our decision-making processes throughout daily life, the same is true of technology integration. For example, think about the complex decision-making factors that go into your decision to exercise. One of the foundational and most important factors is if you believe it to be necessary and if you have a positive attitude towards exercise. This example correlates well to technology integration. The first step towards effective technology integration is if the integrator believes technology to be useful and they have a positive attitude towards technology use. To put it another way, the teacher's attitudes and beliefs serve as a filter through which they take in and apply relevant information. This demonstrates the direct impact attitudes and beliefs play in the technology integration process (Chen, 2008). It is not only theoretical, but attitudes and beliefs are directly applicable. These beliefs highlight the need to focus on higher-level goals without getting bogged down with how-to tutorials. Too often, the first two beliefs are skipped when attempting to integrate technology. The third belief is also significant and emphasizes the need for teacher training to utilize technology and resources to accomplish the intended goals. The three beliefs work together to formulate a solid foundation for effective technology integration. Contextual factors also play a significant role in a teacher's beliefs about technology integration. Some of the examples include school culture, demonstrating the tool, and policy (Chen, 2008). This shows that to best understand teacher beliefs they need to be considered along with contextual factors. Oftentimes, contextual factors are guided by school leaders such as providing avenues for teachers to observe technology integration in another classroom or contextual examples can come from the school community that encourages or discourages technology integration. TEXAS Principal and Supervisor Association (2022) reported about the interesting dilemma that occurs when some teachers attempt to integrate technology. Espoused beliefs towards student-centered learning do not translate when they utilize technology. A teacher creates engaging hands-on activities where students produce powerful demonstrations of their learning, but when that same teacher utilizes technology, the classroom activities transform into a worksheet or drill-based exercise (Ertmer et al., 2012). This brings to the forefront an important point for consideration about transitioning a teacher's pedagogical beliefs within their technology integration. Teachers need time and assistance when applying their teaching practices within the scope of technology integration. In addition, the teachers' lived experiences and perceptions of teachers on using digital technology in classroom instruction are about the first themes of attitudes and beliefs. Those who

grew up with technology are generally more confident and willing to experiment. But for many veteran teachers, it's been a journey of adaptation. Teachers' perception of technology in education varies depending on their subject area. In my school, math and science teachers were more likely to embrace digital tools early on, while some humanities teachers initially hesitated. It took time to demonstrate the benefits, and now we have a more balanced approach across the board. The teachers' lived experiences and perceptions of teachers using digital technology in classroom instruction de-

velop with the common theme of welcoming attitudes and beliefs. Some teachers view it as a threat to traditional teaching methods, while others see it as a valuable enhancement. Bridging this gap requires professional development and support, but it's fascinating to witness how teachers' beliefs can shift over time as they become more proficient in using technology. On the other hand, during the process, the discussions were observed to have additional common experiences and themes. These were subjected to a series of scrutinizes to have a clear understanding.

3.0.2. Needs professional development— The narration of teachers' lived experiences, perceptions of teachers on using digital technology in classroom instruction and the first theme of attitudes and beliefs. When teachers can see how a particular technology tool directly enhances their teaching or benefits students, they tend to embrace it more readily. It's all about making the connection between technology and learning outcomes. These responses reflected in the range of attitudes and beliefs teachers hold regarding using digital technology in classroom instruction. It's essential to recognize that these attitudes can evolve over time as teachers gain more experience and training in integrating technology into their teaching practices. Supported by the ideas of Darling-Hammond, Hyler, and Gardner, (2017) have examined different models and approaches to professional development, exploring their impact on teachers' knowledge, skills, and confidence in using digital tools in the elementary classroom. However, I've come to appreciate how it can supplement and enhance what we do over time. It's about finding the right balance. Additional narrations of teachers-participants about needs professional development. One of the most significant shifts I've noticed in my colleagues is the move from resistance to adap-

tion. However, I've seen these generational gaps narrowing as professional development opportunities have increased, allowing everyone to develop more positive beliefs about technology in education. Need for professional development. Teachers' attitudes toward technology often depend on their exposure to it during their own education. Those with limited access to technology during their schooling may be more hesitant. However, as we've integrated it into our teaching, even those with initial reservations have seen the benefits and come to appreciate its role in education. With the narration above, I analyzed teachers' lived experiences of using digital technology in classroom instruction to develop a second theme: professional development. These responses provide additional insights into teachers' lived experiences of using digital technology in the classroom, especially in terms of their need for professional development. It was clear that there was a diversity of views among educators, and these views can change as they gain more exposure and experience with technology in education. As I analyzed the narration, I noticed that this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring teachers' perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, as well as the second theme of effective professional devel-

opment programs. These responses highlight the impact of needs professional development programs on teachers' lived experiences and perceptions regarding the use of digital technology in the classroom. Well-designed and meaningful professional development can be crucial in fostering positive attitudes and beliefs about technology integration in education. Supported by San Jose, (2020) ideas, this study aims to explore how teachers perceive the use of digital technology in their classrooms, examining their attitudes towards technology integration, perceived benefits and drawbacks, levels of confidence, and professional development needs. By exploring teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and experiences, this research seeks to shed light on the potential of digital technology to improve teaching practices, engage students, and foster

meaningful learning experiences in the elementary education landscape (Dela Cruz, and Barrot, J 2019). On the other hand, teachers' lived experiences and perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction develop a third theme, which points to barriers and challenges. It made us realize that technology can be a valuable tool, not just for emergencies but for everyday teaching, too. Teachers' attitudes have shifted toward embracing it as a permanent part of our instructional toolkit. As I analyzed the narration, I saw that this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring teachers' lived experiences and perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction. This emerged as the third theme of effective barriers and challenges.

3.0.3. Barriers and Challenges—It helps us see the practical benefits of technology and leads to a more positive view of its role in the classroom; effective professional development programs often create a supportive community of learners among teachers. Barriers and Challenges. Successful integration requires identifying teachers' obstacles and challenges when using digital technology in the elementary class-

room. Research has examined factors such as lack of access to technology, inadequate infrastructure, time constraints, and the need for ongoing technical support and training (Eickelmann and Vennemann, 2018). We share our experiences, successes, and challenges, which can be enlightening. This sense of collaboration has transformed our perceptions of technology from a solitary endeavor to a collective effort to improve student learning.

As I analyzed the narration, I realized that this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the lived experiences of teachers lived experiences, their perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, and the third theme of effective professional development programs. I've found that professional development programs need to be flexible and adaptable. As technology evolves, so should our training. The best pro-

grams continuously update their content to keep us current, and this ongoing support has been instrumental in shaping our perceptions of technology as a dynamic and evolving tool in education. Shown in Figure 3 are the teachers' lived experiences with using digital technology in classroom instruction, and the emerge of common themes, namely, welcoming attitudes and beliefs towards technological advancement,

3.1. The Teachers Coping with The Challenges of Exploring Digital Technology in Classroom Instruction—

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of teachers’ lived experiences using digital technology in classroom instruction

The second objective of this study is for teachers coping with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher’s coping mechanism with the challenges teachers exploring digital technology in classroom instruction the three major themes such as Pedagogical Approaches, Challenges and Barriers, and Student Outcomes. Therefore, the research questions in the study dealt with how teachers cope with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers’ coping mechanisms with the challenges, teachers exploring digital technology in classroom instruction emerged with the theme of pedagogical approaches. As I analyzed the narration from participants A1, A2, A3, and A5, I found that their way of coping with the barriers and challenges in dealing with this digital technology was innovative pedagogical development. These responses illustrate the coping mechanisms that one thing teachers appreciate about innovations in professional development. It was clearly emphasized how to address their individual needs in dealing with digital tech-

nology problems. Generally, I analyzed the narration of teachers that this would serve as their coping mechanism with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction; I found that a major theme that would balance the demands of technology integration with the traditional curriculum has been a significant challenge. Our coping strategy involves collaborating with subject-area peers to align technology with curriculum goals. By working together, we’ve bridged the gap and made technology a more natural part of our teaching. They highlight the importance of assessment, communication with parents, differentiation, professional development, collaboration, flexibility, and effective classroom management in addressing student outcomes, innovation, and classroom culture. These responses highlight teachers’ various pedagogical approaches to cope with challenges when exploring digital technology in classroom instruction. These approaches emphasize student engagement, differentiated learning, critical thinking, and responsible technology use as strategies to overcome technological obstacles in the learning environment. On the other hand, another discovery came from the

mouth of the participants that their coping mechanism was for teachers to cope with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' coping mechanisms with the challenges, teachers exploring digital technology in classroom instruction emerged with the theme of supporting students' engagement towards digital learning activities. Here is their narrative statement:

I analyzed the narration that often involves preparing the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges interview data gathered from the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers exploring digital technology in classroom instruction the theme supporting student's engagement towards digital learning activities. Since deliberate practice requires students to stretch themselves to a higher level of performance, it requires complete concentration and is effortful to maintain for extended periods (van Gog et al., 2005). Such deliberate practice activities must be at an appropriate and challenging difficulty level and enable successive refinement by allowing for repetition, giving room to make and correct errors, and providing informative feedback to a learner (Hattie, 2009). In a meta-analysis of online learning studies, Means et al. (2009) found that students' time on a task was significantly higher in online and blended courses than in face-to-face learning environments. This findings was supported by the following study of Barnacle and Dall'Alba, (2017); Kahu Nelson (2018) and Koranteng et al., (2019) stressed that though the current generation of students entering univer-

Educational Insights and Practices Can Be Drawn from The Findings, which have emerged major themes such as digital pedagogy, Instructional Practices, Contextual Factors, And Differentiated Instruction Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher, explore educational

sity has a certain level of digital literacy, such literacy might be limited to engaging with entertainment technologies and games rather than using such skills to acquire vital knowledge and skills (Prior et al., 2016). Since engagement is associated with academic achievement, researchers have identified various strategies to support better engagement. However, the meaning of student engagement means different things to different people. Also, there is limited understanding of how students engage with learning technologies and the extent to which engagement with such technologies fosters enhanced learning outcomes Reyes, A., Santos, L., and Hernandez, M. (2023). Teachers' Perceptions of Digital Technology Integration: A Case Study of Elementary Schools in Metro Manila. *Philippine Journal of Educational Technology*. This case study investigated teachers' perceptions of digital technology integration in elementary schools in Metro Manila, Philippines. It explored the factors influencing teachers' perceptions, their confidence levels, and the extent to which digital technology was being utilized in the classroom. Therefore the study implied based on the narrative statement of the participants stated that practice self-care to prevent burnout; managing stress is essential when adapting to new teaching methodologies. Maintain a healthy work-life balance and allocate time for professional development without overwhelming oneself. Continuously assess the effectiveness of digital tools and pedagogical approaches through student performance and feedback. Be willing to adapt and change strategies if they are not yielding the desired outcomes.

insight or tools drawn from the study of teachers' perceptions of using digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme of digital pedagogy and instructional practices. As I analyzed the narration of the teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be

Fig. 4. How do teachers cope with the challenges in exploring digital technology in classroom instruction

drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme digital pedagogy and instructional practices. The insights of the teachers’ participants are obvious that these

insights can inform the development of digital pedagogy and instructional practices, helping educators leverage technology to create meaningful and impactful learning experiences for their students.

3.1.1. Digital Pedagog and Instructional Practices—These responses highlight the educational insights and practical tools that teachers can draw from the study of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme digital pedagogy and instructional practices. As I analyzed the narration of the teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme digital pedagogy and instructional practices. Studies have explored various aspects, such as teachers’ approaches to lesson planning, strategies for promoting student engagement, and the use of digital tools for differentiating instruction. Student Outcomes: Explore research that exam-

ines the perceived impact of digital technology integration on student learning outcomes in elementary classrooms. Look for studies that investigate teachers’ perceptions of improved academic achievement, critical thinking skills, creativity, and motivation among students (Mouza, C., Lavigne, N. 2021). On the other hand, the study is to explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme contextual factors. As I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn

from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme contextual factors. The narrative of participants implied that the educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme contextual factors is a helpful tool of teachers to make more effective in teaching learning process. As I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme contextual factors is a factors that the teachers participants valued as helpful contributors for teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, based on the teachers responses and after saturated. As I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme contextual factors, factors that the teachers participants valued as helpful contributors for teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, based on the teachers responses and after saturated, differently implied based on the two participants that they always integrate digital technology in classroom instruction in their teaching approach. As I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study on perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme contextual factors. Factors that the teachers participants valued as helpful contributors for teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, based on the teachers responses and after saturated, differently implied based on the two participants that they always integrate digital technology in classroom instruction in their teaching approach. Access to reliable and up-to-date technology: Teachers emphasized the importance of having access to reliable and up-to-date technology in the classroom. This includes computers, tablets, projectors, and other devices that can support digital instruction. Professional development opportunities: Participants also valued professional development opportunities that focused on digital technology integration. These opportunities provided teachers with the skills and knowledge they needed to effectively incorporate technology into their lessons. Collaboration and support from colleagues: Teachers highlighted the importance of collaboration and support from colleagues when it came to using digital technology in the classroom. This included sharing resources, lesson plans, and troubleshooting issues that arose during instruction. Student engagement and motivation: Finally, participants noted that digital technology had a positive impact on student engagement and motivation in the classroom. By incorporating interactive tools and multimedia elements into their lessons, teachers were able to create more dynamic learning experiences for their students. Overall, these factors highlight the importance of providing teachers with the resources, training, and support they need to effectively integrate digital technology into their teaching practice. By doing so, we can help ensure that students are prepared for success in today's increasingly digital world. These claims are supported with the results of the study of Manalo, E. G., Tiu, R. D. (2020). revealed that play-based learning was a highly regarded strategy in these classrooms and that teachers understood its advantages for the all-round development of young children. By studying teachers'

responses within the framework of contextual factors, researchers can gain valuable insights into the nuanced challenges and innovative solutions educators employ when integrating digital technology into their classrooms. These insights can inform policymaking, resource allocation, and the development of tailored educational tools, ensuring that digital initiatives are effective, inclusive, and culturally responsive. On the other hand, the study aims to explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teacher perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme of differentiated instruction. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher, explore educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teachers' perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme of differentiated instruction. I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teachers' perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme of differentiated instruction. I found that the teachers' perceptions of digital technology varied greatly. Some believed it was a valuable tool for differentiated instruction,

allowing for personalized learning experiences for each student. Others, however, felt it was a distraction and hindered student engagement. I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teachers' perceptions of the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme of differentiated instruction. Despite these differing opinions, one thing was clear: the importance of teacher training in using digital technology. Many teachers desired more professional development opportunities to improve their skills and knowledge. I analyzed the narration of teachers exploring educational insight or tools that can be drawn from the study of teachers' perceptions of teachers on the use of digital technology in classroom instruction, considering the theme of differentiated instruction. Additionally, it became apparent that the successful implementation of digital technology in classroom instruction required teacher training and adequate resources and support from school administrators. Overall, my analysis highlighted the need for ongoing research and discussion on the role of digital technology in education and how it can be effectively utilized to enhance student learning.

3.1.2. Differentiated Instruction—The impact of digital technology on differentiated instruction. Strategies for integrating digital technology in the classroom for differentiated instruction. Challenges and barriers to implementing digital technology in differentiated instruction. Best practices for using digital technology to support differentiated instruction As I continued analyzing the study, I found that digital technology significantly impacted differentiated instruction. Teachers who effectively integrated technology into their teaching reported higher student engagement and motivation. However, there were challenges and

barriers to implementing digital technology in the classroom, such as lack of access or training. To overcome these challenges, teachers can use strategies such as providing multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement through technology tools. For example, using interactive whiteboards or online platforms can allow students to access information differently and collaborate with peers. Overall, the study highlights the potential benefits of using digital technology to support differentiated instruction in the classroom while acknowledging the need for thoughtful planning and implementation. Lopez, A. (2022). *Differentiated Instruc-*

Fig. 5. Educational management insights are drawn from the study

tion Approaches to Digital In terms of best practices, it is essential for teachers to regularly assess student progress and adjust their use of technology accordingly. Additionally, providing opportunities for student choice and voice in technology use can increase motivation and ownership over their learning. This study in-

vestigated the perspectives of Filipino teachers on student-centered approaches to digital technology integration in elementary classrooms. It explored teachers’ perceptions of student engagement, collaborative learning, and personalized instruction facilitated by digital technology tools and resources.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in culturally responsive teachers through the lens of classroom advisers are also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The study’s findings are based on the data gathered from ten (10) public elementary school faculty line-up participants who were still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The participants would join for an in-depth interview (IDI). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools purposefully chosen. The findings disclosed that the first objective of this study was to learn about teachers’ lived experiences and perceptions of using digital technology in classroom instruction. The study would specifically seek

to answer the following questions: three significant themes: attitudes and beliefs, professional development, and effective professional development programs. The second objective of this study is for teachers coping with the challenges of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers’ coping mechanisms with the difficulties of exploring digital technology in classroom instruction, the three significant themes are pedagogical approaches, challenges and barriers, and student outcomes. The third

objective of this study was to explore educational management insights and practices that can be drawn from the study findings. The study would specifically seek to answer the question of what educational insights and practices can be drawn from the study findings, which have emerged major themes such as digital pedagogy and instructional practices, contextual factors, and differentiated instruction. Therefore, the study his study aimed to understand how teachers perceive the use of digital technology in their classrooms. The study will focus on three main themes: attitudes and beliefs, professional development, and effective professional development programs. Additionally, the study

will explore how teachers cope with the challenges of using digital technology in their instruction through pedagogical approaches, challenges and barriers, and student outcomes. Finally, the study sought to draw educational insights from its findings regarding digital pedagogy, instructional practices, contextual factors, and differentiated instruction. Essentially, this research was trying to learn what teachers think about using technology in their teaching practice and explore ways they can improve it. It also looks at what we could learn from these experiences for better education management practices.

4.2. Implications—The research highlights teachers' perceptions of using digital technology in classroom instruction. Understanding teachers' attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions towards digital technology can help design targeted training programs. Teacher training initiatives can more effectively integrate digital tools into classroom instruction by addressing specific concerns and misconceptions. Insights into effective professional development programs can lead to the creation of more tailored and impactful training modules. Educators could bene-

fit from programs that address challenges faced while integrating digital technology, ultimately improving their teaching methods. Hence, the study's implications extended to teacher training, professional development, pedagogical innovation, student outcomes, policymaking, contextually relevant approaches, and the promotion of lifelong learning. Addressing these areas can contribute significantly to successfully integrating digital technology in classroom instruction, ultimately enhancing the quality of education students provide.

4.3. Future Directions—The study's findings have important implications for various aspects of education, including teacher training programs, professional development initiatives, pedagogical innovation, addressing challenges and barriers faced by teachers when integrating technology into their teaching methods, improving student outcomes through the effective use of digital tools, influencing educational policies related to technology integration in schools at different levels such as allocating resources for infrastructure, encouraging contextually relevant approaches tailored specifically to each ed-

ucational setting's unique needs and resources while promoting lifelong learning among educators. Overall, this research can significantly enhance the quality of education provided to students by successfully integrating digital technologies into classroom instruction. One potential area for future research is the impact of teacher leadership and peer mentoring programs on student achievement. By examining how these initiatives affect student learning outcomes, researchers can better understand the overall effectiveness of technology integration in the classroom. Additionally, exploring the

role of school administrators in supporting and promoting teacher-led initiatives could provide valuable insights into how to create a culture of innovation within schools. Ultimately, continued investigation into these areas can help ensure that students receive the best possible education and are prepared for success in an increasingly digital world. By delving into these future directions, researchers can contribute to improving digital technology integration in classrooms, ensuring that educational practices remain relevant, effective, and supportive of both teachers and students.

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